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Fabrication of quasi-2D shape-tailored microparticles using wettability contrast-based platforms

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1 **Keywords:** ultrathin microparticles, quasi-2D nanostructures, oleophobic patterned
2 surfaces, wettable-dewettable contrast, bioinspired surfaces
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4 **Abstract**
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7 The ability to fabricate materials with ultrathin architectures enabled the breakthrough
8 of low dimensional structures with high surface area that showcase distinctive
9 properties from their bulk counterparts. Those have been exploited in a wide range of
10 fields, including energy harvesting, catalysis, and biomedicine. Despite such versatility,
11 the fine tuning of the lateral dimensions and geometry of these structures remains
12 challenging. Pre-patterned platforms gained significant attention as enabling
13 technologies to process materials with highly controlled shapes and dimensions. Herein,
14 different nanometer-thick particles of various lateral sizes and geometries (e.g., squares,
15 circles, triangles, hexagons) were processed with high precision and definition, resorting
16 to wettability contrast of oleophilic-oleophobic patterned surfaces. Quasi-2D polymeric
17 microparticles with high shape- and size-fidelity could be retrieved as freestanding
18 objects in a single step. These structures showed cell-mediated pliability, and their
19 integration in gravity-enforced human adipose-derived stems cells spheroids led to an
20 enhanced metabolic activity and a modulated secretion of pro-angiogenic factors.
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Ultrathin architectures have gained increasing attention for the development of technologies in numerous fields, which has brought into focus the design of low-dimensional structures composed of a myriad of materials, including polymers. Owing to their reduced thickness, the physical and chemical properties of extremely thin materials are amenable to be modulated in a high portion of the whole material itself. This principle has been applied to design materials that outperform the ones processed using bulk architectures, such as spherical particles.^[1] The most exploited property of ultrathin materials is their high aspect ratio and high surface area-to-volume ratio. Owing to their maximized surface area and possibility of exposing an abundant amount of active site moieties,^[2] these materials have been adapted for applications that include highly effective sensors and catalytic platforms for the scale-up of reactions. Other applications that benefit from the high surface area of ultrathin materials include scavenging platforms, such as energy harvesting systems,^[3] and adsorbents^[4] able to effectively capture and isolate contaminants or other species of interest via chemical affinity. Furthermore, the extensive interface displayed by these flat materials can also enable their action as surfactants to stabilize Pickering emulsions, in which a physical barrier between the two immiscible phases prevents droplet coalescence preserving their ‘balanced’ dispersion within the continuous phase.^[5]

The extremely reduced thickness of ultrathin films, ranging from tens to several hundred of nanometers,^[1,6] confer them with thickness-dependent behavior, which typically culminates in high flexibility. Such compliant nature can be appealing to many different applications ranging from wearable soft electronics^[7] to injectable systems in regenerative medicine strategies, acting as minimally invasive implantation units.^[6,8] These highly pliable ‘sheets’ have also been geometrically reconfigured, through folding or bending, into origami-inspired three-dimensional (3D) assemblies.^[9–11] Another particular feature is the possibility of processing them as heterofunctional units, as they present two opposing interfaces amenable to be tailored in order to present asymmetric properties on each side, resulting in different functions.^[4,12] Additional potential of ultrathin structures to be used as tissue sealants aimed at replacing surgical sutures may be assigned to their non-covalent adhesiveness.^[13] This property is particularly interesting for severely damaged tissues, as in cases of burn wounds, where sutures are

1 impractical, those may also act as a physical barrier against infections.^[14]

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3 Among several techniques to assemble nanometer-level materials, the layer-by-
4 layer (LbL) technology^[15] and the Langmuir-Blodgett method^[16] are noteworthy, as both
5 systems allow fabricating complex architectures at the molecular level, relying on a
6 variety of interaction chemistries, enabling excellent thickness control in the nanoscale.
7 However, these techniques are time-consuming and require multiple steps. Another
8 methods, such as spin- and dip-coating, may provide simpler and faster ways of
9 assembling freestanding ultrathin structures based on the use of (i) sacrificial layers or
10 (ii) cast/supporting layer techniques, followed by a single step polymer deposition.^[17,18]
11 These techniques, however, often limit the control over samples' lateral size at the
12 micrometer-scale and, most relevantly, over their geometry. Approaches based on pre-
13 patterned platforms able to confine deposited solutions offer the potential to control
14 the lateral dimensions of materials, as well as their overall shape.^[19,20]

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17 Here, we report the development of monodisperse ultrathin polymeric particles,
18 with several hundred nanometers of thickness and highly controlled micrometer-range
19 lateral sizes (50-500 μm). Freestanding micro-objects assorted with different
20 geometries and sizes were obtained resorting to a high-density microdroplet array of
21 low-surface-tension liquids, exploiting for the first time their contrasting wettability
22 properties to produce detachable objects.^[21] We developed an easy and straightforward
23 method to produce highly tailorable freestanding microparticles, which supported cell
24 adhesion and expansion, while tailoring the secreting properties of mesenchymal stem
25 cell spheroids.

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28 Micropatterned surfaces based on the localized control of wettability of organic
29 liquids were prepared as previously described.^[21] Those enabled the deposition of
30 polymeric solutions on wettable spots of geometrically defined patterns, surrounded by
31 non-wettable regions. While the latter region repels the liquid or solution, the wettable
32 domains, driven by surface tension, can hold it, such that the contact line of the liquid is
33 pinned along the frame of the patterns.^[22] A methodology based on a sequential dip-
34 coating process into two different polymer solutions was developed. While the first
35 deposited polymer acted as a sacrificial layer, the second deposited polymer could be

1 released as a freestanding structure after solvent drying. The selection of polymers with
2 solubility in different solvents enabled to employ the experimental procedure depicted
3 in **Figure 1a**. In a first step, the pristine pre-patterned surface was immersed in a
4 poly(acrylic acid) (PAA) solution prepared in a mixture of ethanol and water. The surface
5 was then immediately and slowly removed from the solution, allowing the dewetting of
6 PAA solution to occur in the wettable arrayed patterns. Upon solvent evaporation,
7 polymer deposition was observed, with strict confinement within the pattern, and
8 recreating its exact shape. Afterwards, the dip-coating and solvent evaporation
9 processes were repeated using a poly- ϵ -caprolactone (PCL) solution to build-up the
10 second layer. The stacking of different polymeric layers is possible since the solvent in
11 which PCL was prepared – dichloromethane - is not amenable to solubilize the
12 previously deposited PAA layer. The sequential deposition of both polymers was
13 confirmed through fluorescence microscopy, using a PAA solution loaded with
14 coumarin-6, and a PCL solution with Nile Red (Figure 1a). In order to yield freestanding
15 PCL microparticles, a single trigger event consisting on the immersion of the platform in
16 a solution of sodium hydroxide (1 M NaOH) was employed. Due to the pH
17 responsiveness-driven molecular reconfiguration and further dissolution of PAA, NaOH
18 was effective on promoting the etching of the sacrificial polymer layer,^[23,24] leading to
19 the release of PCL microparticles from the glass substrate into the solution. A mild
20 mechanical stimulation, such as agitation or simply creating a flow while pipetting the
21 solution up-and-down, can be applied to speed up the process to few seconds (Movie
22 S1, Supporting Information). The dimension and shape of the dried PCL particles was
23 dictated by the wettable pattern, and thus by the photomask design. Consequently, it
24 was possible to produce both on-chip and freestanding particles with different sizes
25 (ranging from 50 to 500 μm) and geometric shapes, including squares, circles, triangles
26 and hexagons (Figure 1b, Figure S1, Supporting Information). The method allowed the
27 formation of sharp-edged particles, in which the definition of the corners could be
28 maintained even after detachment. Furthermore, to validate the versatility of this
29 technique - polymer-wise -, freestanding polystyrene (PS) and poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA)
30 microparticles were also fabricated (Figure S1, Supporting Information). The same
31 conditions were applied for polymer deposition and detachment as the ones used for
32 PCL particles validation, except in the case of PLLA release. Due to the susceptibility of

1 the polymer to higher pH values, leading to particle disintegration, a 0.1 M NaOH
2 solution was used.
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5 The morphology and topography of both circular and square particles with
6 lateral sizes of 200 μm , on-chip and freestanding, was performed by 3D optical
7 profilometry analysis. Two different approaches were employed to quantitatively assess
8 the fidelity of the polymer pinning efficiency within the patterned domains and, thus, to
9 evaluate the precision and accuracy of the deposition over the patterns: (i)
10 measurement of the size of the particles: diameter for circles, and side dimension for
11 squares (**Figure 2a**), and (ii) measurement of the shape: roundness for circles, and aspect
12 ratio for squares (Figure 2b).^[25] On-chip particles showed over 95% size fidelity for both
13 circles and squares, which indicates that polymer deposition led to the highly accurate
14 recreation of the chemically imprinted pattern. In turn, for the freestanding particles the
15 fidelity score was around 93%, and particle dimensions became more scattered. This
16 dispersion in size may be associated with the NaOH treatment used to detach the
17 particles from the surface, as strong bases may hydrolyze ester bonds, hence, slightly
18 degrading the PCL structure.^[26] Similarly, a shape fidelity over 97% was obtained for on-
19 chip particles, while freestanding particles displayed a decrease of less than 3%. This
20 clearly demonstrates the efficiency of the method to produce particles with very precise
21 shapes with well-defined and sharp edges as in the case of the squares (Figure 2c).
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39 The thickness of the materials deposited in the wettable patterns was measured
40 in three different stages: (i) after the deposition and drying of the sacrificial PAA layer,
41 (ii) after the build-up of both polymers (PAA + PCL), and (iii) for the PCL particles alone
42 as freestanding objects. Two distinct regions – edges and center - were measured for
43 these three different conditions, as the deposition of the polymer was not uniformly
44 distributed throughout the individual patterned regions because of the coffee ring
45 effect. Initially, the thickness profile of polymer solutions within the patterned domains
46 was convex due to liquid droplet morphology. Conversely, upon solvent evaporation the
47 profile displayed a concave morphology. This phenomenon is known as the coffee-ring-
48 like effect and describes how the evaporation of the droplet occurs, and how it
49 influences polymer deposition. An enhanced evaporation rate is observed at the droplet
50 edge, which leads to an outward flow of the solvent, driving the movement of solutes
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1 towards the contact line and creating a ring-shaped deposition.^[27] For the analysis
2 presented here, an approximate average particle thickness was considered and
3 calculated as the arithmetic mean between the maximum value found within the edges
4 and the minimum value in the center. In the case of PAA deposition, the measured
5 thickness is significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) for squares (ca. 80 nm) comparatively with
6 circles (ca. 60 nm) (Figure 2d). This substantial change can be explained by the
7 differences in the area exhibited by both patterned geometries. The area displayed by
8 the square patterns is higher than the circular ones, thus, square patterns have the
9 capacity to hold a larger droplet, therefore containing more solute. Concerning the
10 deposition of PCL over the sacrificial layer, three different concentrations - 2%, 3.5%, 5%
11 (w/v) - were used. A general tendency shows that particles' thickness increased with the
12 increase in polymer concentration, both for circular and square geometries (Figure 2e).
13 Moreover, the morphology of the microparticles displayed a decrease of the coffee-ring
14 effect with increasing PCL concentration. The interval in thickness ranged from ca. 100
15 nm up to ca. 300 nm, for the lowest and highest PCL concentration, respectively.
16 Therefore, both thickness and topography can be tailored by tuning polymer
17 concentration. To evaluate the thickness of the freestanding structures, only 5% (w/v)
18 PCL formulation was considered, as those were the easiest particles to handle and
19 displayed the highest thickness along with a less prominent coffee-ring (Figure 2f). Both
20 square and circle geometries showed an approximate thickness of 200 nm. Moreover,
21 those exhibited polydispersity indexes (PDI) of 0.038 and 0.033 for circles and squares,
22 respectively, revealing a highly monodisperse distribution (Figure 2d-f).^[28] The
23 morphology of circles and squares is displayed in Figure 2g. An additional approach
24 based on a sequential dipping strategy was employed to investigate the possibility of
25 further tuning particles' thickness. Two solvents with contrasting solubility for PCL -
26 dichloromethane (high solubility) and acetone (low solubility) - were applied to perform
27 sequential dipping. The growth of the films' thickness showed an inconsistent behavior,
28 as the increase of the number of dipping steps was not fully translated into an increase
29 in thickness (Figure S2, Supporting Information).

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The behavior of the freestanding 5% PCL ultrathin films while in contact with cells
was explored. Conventional microparticulate systems used for the expansion of

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adherent cells often show static geometric properties over time. To test the hypothesis of the microparticles' pliability related to their ultra-thinness, MC3T3-E1 cells were cultured on top of the microparticles (**Figure 3a i**). Those were easily twisted and folded after 24 hours of culture, in a phenomenon solely mediated by cell-surface interactions, and by the flexibility of the supporting object (**Figure 3a ii**). In a second approach, 30 to 50 PCL ultrathin particles were added to cellular suspensions, which were used to prepare gravity-enforced 3D cell aggregates (**Figure 3b i** and **3b ii**). Such kind of assemblies are in line with bottom-up strategies of producing hybrid tissues that could be used for biomedicine, including tissue engineering.^[29,30] Both, all-cellular hASCs aggregates, as well as microparticle-containing aggregates, showed identical diameters: $469 \pm 33 \mu\text{m}$ and $491 \pm 48 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, at day 1, decreasing about 20% of their original size at day 3 (**Figure 3 iii**). The decrease in spheroid diameter was probably related to spheroids contraction, which led to increasing compactness overtime, culminating in a more circular morphology overtime (**Figure S3**, Supporting Information). The addition of microparticles to hASCs aggregates did not compromise the formation of cellular spheroids with typical shape and morphology. The hydrophilization of PCL microparticles by the NaOH treatment exposed carboxylated groups at the surface, increasing its surface energy, necessary for cells to adhere.^[26] Upon cell adherence and spheroid formation, the particles are effortlessly twisted by the cells due to their ultra-thinness and not-stiff morphology. The cross-section of the spheroids (**Figure 3b iv**) depicts a moderate roughness in the interior of both control and microparticle-containing conditions, seemingly caused by densely packed cells during spheroid compaction. Throughout the inner surface of the microparticle-loaded spheroid, quasi-transparent structures, which were here identified as microparticles, could be observed throughout the whole aggregate. The Live/Dead staining of the spheroids (**Figure S4 a**, Supporting Information) unveiled that the outer-layer cells remained viable both at day 1 and 3, independently of the presence of particles within the cell aggregate. Due to the insufficient oxygen diffusion and nutrient exchange with the medium, both spheroids exhibit an overly developed necrotic core. Nonetheless, inspecting the metabolic activity (**Figure 3b v**), cells remained metabolically active in both conditions and, at day 3, this activity showed a 2-fold increase ($p < 0.05$) for spheroids containing particles. The fluorescent labeling of the sheet-like particles

1 allowed their identification through confocal microscopy in particle-containing
2 spheroids (Figure 3b vi). The cross-section of the aggregate revealed embedded particles
3 throughout the whole core of the structure, possibly wrapping up cells. Spheroids with
4 particles also showed higher levels of VEGF released from hASCs (Figure 3b vii) when
5 compared to cell spheroids alone. Although VEGF secretion decreased from day 1 to day
6 3 in both conditions, particle-free aggregates exhibited a more abrupt decline of 76%
7 ($p < 0.05$), whereas aggregates incorporating particles showed 50% of decrease (non-
8 significant), disclosing that the incorporation of particles into hASCs spheroids had a
9 positive effect on prolonging and supporting the continuously release of the soluble
10 factor over time. Solely in the presence of bare and non-functionalized PCL particles, the
11 performance and secretion profile of hASCs was modulated without the need of any
12 additional cell behavioral influencers. These findings reveal that these structures may
13 be explored as potential pro-angiogenic structures.^[31] β 1-integrin has been reported to
14 modulate cell function seeded onto biomaterials with different surface chemistries
15 (including NH_2 - and OH-rich surfaces^[32]) and also to be involved in promoting VEGF
16 secretion through MAPK/ERK signaling pathway^[33]. We hypothesized that the
17 incorporation of particles within the cellular structure would potentiate and activate
18 stronger β 1-integrin-mediated interactions by introducing an OH-rich and high surface-
19 area material into the construct. In this sense, we hypothesized that by blocking β 1-
20 integrin, part of cell-ECM (and possibly cell-microparticles) binding would be impaired,
21 which could give us insight about the role of these interactions in the mediation of VEGF
22 release. Although blocking β 1-integrin on hASCs prior to spheroid formation led to a
23 systematic decrease on secreted VEGF, this trend was not statistically significant in any
24 of the studied timepoints (Table S5, Supporting Information). Moreover, the decrease
25 observed for both microparticle-containing and microparticle-free spheroids was
26 similar, indicating that either β 1-integrin does not significantly mediate hASCs-
27 microparticle adhesion, or that this effect does not directly correlate with VEGF
28 secretion. Importantly, even when blocked for β 1-integrin, hASCs incorporated the
29 microparticles in the structure of the spheroid. To further investigate the role of
30 microparticles in the secreting properties of the spheroids, structures containing a lower
31 mass of microparticles (represented as PCL<) were prepared. Interestingly, a reduction
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1 of microparticle mass by half led to the same effect on VEGF secretion when compared
2 to spheroids containing a higher mass of particles (Table S5, Supporting Information).
3 We hypothesize that the maintenance of VEGF secretion on cell aggregates after 3 days
4 of culture may rely on the role of microparticles as providers of hypoxic cues - well-
5 reported to induce the secretion of VEGF in hASCs^[34] - due to their high and probably
6 oxygen-impermeable surface area^[35].
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12 In summary, we demonstrate the fabrication of sheet-like microparticles
13 encompassing a vast array of geometries with high precision, high throughput and
14 definition, using a straightforward and scalable method. The technique is compatible
15 with different types of materials, either for the sacrificial or the freestanding “to be”
16 layers. Moreover, the overall thickness of the freestanding particles could be controlled
17 by varying polymer concentration. Gravity-enforced spheroids containing these quasi-
18 2D cell-deformed pliable particles show enhanced metabolic activity, without hindering
19 the typical spheroid formation, morphology and morphometric features. The formed
20 cell-particle structures could also act as a platform for the release of angiogenic factors.
21 Besides their potential application as highly reactive surfaces in green chemistry and
22 energy harvesting approaches, these geometrically controlled ultrathin microparticles
23 may act as valuable elements in the design of “low-biomaterial” living structures, which
24 may integrate human tissue for therapies or disease models - through the tailoring of
25 their physicochemical and geometrical features to drive specific cell functions, possibly
26 through the modulation of cell-mediated folding patterns.^[36]
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43 **Supporting Information**

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45 Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the
46 author.
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Figures

Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of the overall experimental procedure for the fabrication of quasi-2D PCL microparticles. The first step encompasses the dip-coating of the surface in a PAA solution, which upon solvent evaporation and polymer deposition, creates the sacrificial layer. Then, the step is repeated using a PCL solution to form a new top layer. Both polymer solutions were stained with different dyes (PAA with coumarin-6 and PCL with Nile Red) and assessed by fluorescence microscopy to confirm the deposition and correct overlay between the layers. b) Assessing the versatility of the developed platform in generating microparticles portraying different sizes and geometries. Each “ l ” represented in every image indicates the lateral size defined to measure particle length. All the acquired images were false-colored using Mountains Lab Premium v8.0 software.

Figure 2. Morphometric characterization and topographic analysis of both circular and square particles ($\ell = 200 \mu\text{m}$). a) Size fidelity score of on-chip and freestanding particles. b) Shape fidelity score of on-chip and freestanding particles (roundness of a perfect circle = 1, and aspect ratio of a perfect square = 1) c. Top-views of on-chip and freestanding particles with an overlapping dashed-line shape (yellow) of a perfect $\ell = 200 \mu\text{m}$ circle and square. d) Thickness of the PAA deposition. The inset represents the estimation of the thickness for all conditions: the mean values were obtained as an arithmetic mean between the maximum and the minimum values. e) Thickness of PAA overlaid with PCL (2%, 3.5%, 5% (w/v)) deposition. f) Thickness of freestanding PCL 5% (w/v) microparticles. A minimum of 75 particles were considered and analyzed per condition. Polydispersity index (PDI) of the thickness measured for all of the conditions indicates that all the particles are highly monodisperse (PDI < 0.05).^[28] g) Profilometric views of the on-chip and freestanding particles, revealing the major morphological and topographical differences. For the statistical analysis the data is presented as mean \pm

standard deviation ($n > 75$ units) and it is considered statistically different when * $p < 0.05$ and **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure 3. a) MC3T3-E1 trigger PCL microparticle folding and twisting. i) Schematic representation of the cell culture. ii) Fluorescence micrograph of a PCL microparticle

1 folded by MC3T3-E1. Cytoskeleton stained with Flash Phalloidin™ Red 594 and nuclei
2 with DAPI. b) *In vitro* biological performance of sheet-like particles within hASCs
3 spheroids. i) Schematic representation of the culture parameters used to assemble
4 hASCs spheroids. ii) Optical microscopy images of hASCs and hASCs/PCL spheroids at
5 different time-points. iii) Spheroid diameter assessment along time-points using ImageJ
6 Software analysis (v1.52n). iv) SEM micrographs of cross-sectioned hASCs and
7 hASCs/PCL spheroids after 24h of culture. White arrows pin-point PCL microparticles
8 within the aggregate. v) Metabolic activity assessment through AlamarBlue™ assay at
9 24h and 72h. vi) CLSM micrograph (optical cross-section) of a hASCs/PCL spheroid,
10 illustrating the particle distribution within the aggregate at day 3. Cells are stained with
11 Flash Phalloidin™ Red 594 (red channel) and DAPI (blue channel), while the particles are
12 stained with coumarin-6. vii) Quantification of secreted VEGF per spheroid into the
13 medium by hASCs and hASCs/PCL spheroids at both times-points. For the statistical
14 analysis the data is presented as mean \pm s.e.m. (n=3) and it is considered statistically
15 different when * $p < 0.05$.